

Life Skills – Approaches to Teach Life and Skills

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Abstract

Life skills have been defined by the adaptation of a positive behaviour have been effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life the life skills processes in all-round development like the challenges in economical, social, political and technological fields.

The present psycho social that determines valued behavior and included reflective skills such has the problem solving and critical thinking.

The main objective towards a meaningful life. The main objective of life skills to face the realities of life and to develop meaningful social relationship to analyze their capacity to enhance the function in a most productively manner.

Life skills reflects in many ways like problem solving, creative thinking, decision making, effective communication, self awareness skills and to cope with the stress there are many ways to develop the decision making ability like reference questions co-relation doesn't equal caution and anticipate to impulsivity etc.

The ways to develop effective communication through the voice, animating the voice enhance towards appropriate volume through the slow down process and eye contact. There are some interpersonal skills like critising, smiling, solving, self awareness in the mean while the cope of stress also accompanied by thought of being in control like a muscle relaxation, focusing and things regular means tallying about problems of adult and friends, scheduling for music arts, socialization. It also enlighten towards empathy and ways of empathy.

Keywords: Life Skills, Adaptation and Positive Behavior, Teach Life
Introduction

Life skills have been defined by the world health organization as "objectives for adaptation and positive behavior that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of every day life".

Education is the process of all round development of an individual education that enables on individual to live his life effectively and successfully. Every individual has certain goals in life. He tries to achieve those goals in this endeavors he/she has to acquire certain skills to lead a happy life in the present democratic society. That encounter a number of challenges in economical social, political and technological fields. These skills are known as life skills in his/her mind while created optimum and challenging learning atmosphere in the classroom situation. Through syllabus competition is one of their primary objectives.

They have to mould the syllabus in the form of learning experience such that life skills are thought internally.

The present psycho-social that determine valued behavior and include reflective skills such as problem solving and critical thinking.

To personal skills such as self awareness and to inter persons skills practicing life skills leads to action competencies to the action and generate change and to capabilities hence the freedom to decide that to do and who to be life skills are thus distinctly different from physical perceptual motor skills such as practical or health skills as well as from living hood skills such as crafts money management and inter premarital skills health and livelihood education however can be designed to be complementary to life skills education and vice-versa.

Aims and objectives of Life Skills

1. To provide students with strategies to make healthy choice that contribute to a meaningful life.
2. To promote mental well being and competence in young people as they face the realities of life.
3. To take positive action to protect themselves and to promote health and meaningful social relationship.

4. To facilitates a complete and integrated development of individuals to function effectively as social being.
5. To understand self and able to assess their skills abilities and areas of developments which also enable them to analyse their capacity to enhance the function in a most productive way.
6. To allows the young get along with other people able to adjust with their environment and make responsible decision which also incorporate to build their values and to communicate effectively.

Meaning of Life Skills

Education is the process of all round development of an individual. Education thus enables an individual to live his life efficiently and successfully.

Every individual has certain goals in life. He want to achieve those goals for that he/she has to acquire certain skills to lead a happy life in the present democratic society that there is a number of a challenges you are facing in your daily life such as economic, social, political and technological fields to achieve our goals use need some skills known as life skills.

The development of life skills is a life long process that starts in childhood and continues thought out end of life.

Definition of Life Skills

'UNICEF' defines life skills as :-

"A behavior change or behavior development approach designed to address a balance of these areas knowledge attitude and skills".

'WHO' defines life skills as :-

"The abilities for adoptive and positive behavior that enable individual to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life".

Types of Life Skills

The word health organization recognized the ten life skills they are :

1. Problem - Solving skill
2. Critical - Thinking skill
3. Creative - Thinking skill
4. Decision - Making skill
5. Effective Communication skills
6. Interpersonal relationship skills
7. Self awareness skills
8. Skill to cope with emotions
9. Skill to cope with stress
10. Empathy

These life skills are pivotal to lead happy and healthy life so that all human resources can be utilized productively. The above mentioned life skills can be described in the following way.....

Problem Solving Skill

One of the most exciting aspects of life is the array of choice that we have on a daily habits some of our decisions are simple some of them are difficult however some choices are challenging and it needs careful thought and consideration.

When we are confronted or facing these types of situation or decision it can be very difficult to decide on the best options.

This is very normal reaction to tough choices in our lives and we all at time experiences a sense of being to decide on some option. However researcher have developed a technique that many people have

found use full when they are trying to make a difficult decision or solve a problem that seems unsolvable. This is having many steps.

Problem Orientation

This step involves recognizing the existing problem and it's difficulty level you have to approach the decision making process with a positive attitude and view the situation as challenge you should try to approach the situation with confidence and make effort to finding as appropriate situation to your problem.

Problem Definition

Before you start to tackle the current problem it is the important to clearly understand the difficulty level and gathering the information about the problem. Step really involves your thinking about the difficulty you can having understanding the problem some people think of problem as a discrepancy between what they want and what the current situation is like it is useful during this stage to think about how the current situation is different from how you would like it to be.

Generation of Alternative Solution

When you start to think of possible solution don't limit yourself think of many possible options as you can even if they seen unrealistic you may want to write a list of possible options or ask others what some solutions they might have for your problem.

Step-4 :- Decision Making

Here you are ready to narrow down some of the options that you have generated in the previous step. It is important that you examine each of the options while examining options member that no problem solution is perfect and we have to choose the best possible solution.

Solution Implementation and Verification

Once you have examined all your options and decided on one that seems to accomplish your goals and minimized the costs them implement that solution and verified that the degree to solving your problem.

Overall we can say that problem solving skill is the ability to identify the problem correctly understanding its source and courses is the first step in solving a problem later the courses have to be reduced at the first stage them the source of the problem have to be handled carefully after words alternative solution have to be thought of the best possible solution can be adopted.

Critical Thinking Skills

Skill of estimation of positive and negative dimension of an experience or event without the influence of personal bias is critical thinking acquiring critical thinking skills helps you to develop more reasoned arguments and draw out the inferences that you need to use your assignment projects and examination questions.

The Stairway to Critical Thinking

The stages and skills involved in critical thinking can be seen as an eight steps stairway to high grades as your thinking skills develops depth and complexity our other study skills will also improve.

Process

Take the information (i.e., in what you have read seen or done)

Understanding

Comprehend they lay points assumptions arguments and evidence presented examine how there key components figure relative to each other

Analyse

Examine how these key components fit together and relate to each other.

Compare

Explore the similarities differences between ideas you are reading about.

Synthesis

Bring together different source of information to serve an argument or idea you are constructing make logical connections between the different source that help you shape and support your ideas.

Evaluation

Assess the worth of an idea in terms of its relevant to your needs the evidence on which it is based and how it relate to other pertinent ideas.

Apply

Use critical thinking transfer the understanding you have gained from your critical evaluation and use in response to questions assignments and projects.

Justify

Use critical thinking to develop arguments draw conclusions make influences and identify implications. So, critical thinking skills gives students the ability to not only understand what they have need or been shown but also to build up to on that knowledge without incremented guidance critical thinking teacher students that knowledge is fluid and build up on it self.

Creative thinking skills

Creative refers to the phenomenon where by a person creates something new (a product a solution a work of art a novel etc..) that has some kind of value. "the ability to form new and original from the available information is creative thinking. This is also called a divergent thinking.

Way of Developing Creative Thinking

Know yourself

There are some situations in your life where new ideas tempt at you (in day dreaming in long trip if you are away from your regular routine) you need to understanding your own personal cycle.

Keep a Notebook Handy

To capture those creative ideas when they come to make its habit to keep a note book on you near your places of work or relaxation and by your bed side.

Delay Criticism

Resist the critique your new idea nothing will inhibit the creative process more than being critical of a new idea when it first emerges this does not mean that criticism judgment and evaluation have no place in the generation of new ideas but they should come into play only at the conclusion of the creative process.

Be Patient

Release idea development does not always go smoothly. Sometimes many false stars and many some times obstacles may try to stop your process some times persistence will succeed in clearing away obstacles to success.

Note Your Success

Record your conclusion opinions on problems you have been thinking about make note of it as the problem may occur in the same or a difference form.

Be Aware

Make a conscious effort to note how others have solved problems keep collecting from newspapers, magazines etc.

Things the problems itself may not be similar to yours the process or principles used in solving the problem may be applicable.

Train Your Mind for Problem Solving

Set a question for yourself for example commit to finding three ways to do something when you get good at that raise your question to fine and so on. Before long you will notice that when a problem presents it self on your mind will automatically run through many different ways of handling it.

Decision Making Skills

Decision making involves taking on appropriate decision after thinking the advantages and disadvantages of a situation and its future consequences.

Way of Developing Decision Making

When Ever Possible Consider Alternative

Our brains are evaluating evidence dispassionately force yourself to generate alternative has demonstrated the values of concern-factual thinking about the opposite helps make better decision.

Reference Questions

Our memories are highly contextual so that the background to array issue are consider has impact on how we view it politicians advertises and other influences are framing extensively to persuade us of their points of view you can fight back by reframing their proportions.

Co-Relation Doesn't Equal Causation

An oldie but a goldie there's a clear co-relation between foot size and being richening your own house and having a better education on the other hand people with smaller feed are skill strengthening with potty training it yet? People with small feet are usually children so of course they have less money don't have their own houses and have been to school yet co-relation does not equal causation

Anticipate Your Impulsivity

The best of intention after break down in the face of vicious temptation people find it difficult to predict just how far off course their emotions can pull them use any method you come to connect your impulsivity cannot credit card avoid the confectionary store it's all about planning ahead.

Effective Communication Skill

Effective communication is the ability to convey the intended thought ideas feelings and expectation and meaning fully.

Way to Improve Effective Communication Skills

Develop Your Voice

A high voice in not perceived to be one of authority in fact a high self voice can make you sound like pray to an aggressive worker who is out to make his/her career at the expensive of any one else.

Slow Down

People will perceive you as nervous and answer of yourself if you take fast however be careful not to show down to the point where people being to finish your sentences just to help your finish.

Animate Your Voice

Avoid a monotone use dynamics your pitch should raise and lower your volume should be soft and loud listened to your local T.V, News anchor take place.

Enunciate Your Words

Speak clearly don't remember if people are always saying hut to you are mumbling.

Use Appropriate Volume

Use volume that is appropriate for the setting speak more softly when you are alone and close speak loud when you are speaking to larger spaces.

Eye Contact

Make your eyes appear to sparkle use good eye contact that will help you good communicability.

Interpersonal Relationship Skills

An interpersonal relation is an association between two or more people that may range from testing to enduring. This association may be based on have salutatory regular business interactions or form of other type of social commitment.

Interpersonal relationship are formed in the context of social cultural and other influence. The context convey from family relative clubs and places of worship.

Way of Developing Interpersonal Relationship

Don't Criticize Complain About People

Instead of feeling people they are doing sometimes wrong consider asking them questions to try to find out why they do, what they do after them an alternative in a way that come across as trying to help.

Solve Your Own Problems By Solving Other People Problems

If you would like someone to do something in a certain way try to figure out how you want might benefit him or her. This works especially well for who work in sales.

Smile

Smiles are infactions they makes others full warm inside and warmer towards you.

If some one is important to you in any ways fell them so this goes for any type of personal relationship including your kids co-workers your friends any one give them what they want and they will have for it

Self Awareness Skills

Self awareness is the ability to know ones strength and weakness objectively and ones likes dislikes attitude correctly. That means knowing oneself as he or she is.

Having self awareness allows you to see where your thoughts and emotions are taking your it also makes changes you want until you are aware in the moment of the control to your thoughts emotions you will have difficulty making charges in the direction of your life.

Development of Self Awareness

Self awareness is developed through practice in focusing your attention on the details of your personality and behavior when you read a book

you are focusing your attention on the conceptual ideas in the book. Thinking and learning to be mindful self aware as learning to domance when learning to names we have to pray attention to how and where our feel more. When you becomes more self aware you initially begins to see aspects of your personality and behavior that you did not notice before.

Self awareness gives power to take ability and only that decided perfect education and right carrier.

Skill to Cope with Stress

Coping with stress is the ability to relieve ones stress constructively without affecting ones moral.

The following are the Skills to Cope with Stress

Taking deep breath accompanied by thought of being in control

1. Progressive muscle relaxation (repeatedly tensing and relaxing large muscle of the body)
2. Setting small goals and breaking tasks into smaller monoquable choices
3. Focusing on things you can control and letting goals of things you cannot control.
4. Exercising and regular meals and avoiding excessive caffeine.
5. Tallying about problems of adults and friends.
6. Lowering un-elastic expectation.
7. Scheduling breaks and enjoyable activities such as music arts sports socializing.

Empathy

Empathy is the ability to image one self in the position of another person and to feel and understand that person and to feel and understand that person happiness and sorrow's empathy is necessary for caring behavior is an emotional and thinking component to have empathy means to feel another feelings.

Ways of Developing Empathy

Imagine

Imagine yourself in that persons situation after another way is to imagine the person as a child after when we consider the person in the valuable stages of childhood our defense tend to lower.

Nurture of Relationship

Make a point to regularly practice caring behaviours with the persons. When you act lovingly towards some one it actually increases your feelings of love as well as your abilities to empathetic with the persons.

Set Aside Your Beliefs Concerns and Personal Agenda

When you are dealing directly with the persons you have. Go to the conversation empathy handed with no personal expectations your only agenda is listening to your partners feelings and laping to understand your partners point of view.

Identifies with their Experiences

When you are dealing directly with the persons you have being to share focus on the feelings and situation that you have experience in the past that are similar. This will depends on your emotional it sight into other personal experiences.

Gain Personal Perspective

This method involves working on your personal identify when you take things personally you can't separate yourself enough to feel the other person pains.

Educational Implications

It gives frequent feed back to the students and provide both cognitive and emotional support for their efforts.

1. It helps the student clearly address issues of uncertainty in judgement making and to examine their assumptions about knowledge and how it is gained.
2. Encourage students to practice their reasoning skill in many settings like student organization residence hall, councils and else where to gain practice and confidence applying their thinking skills.
3. Helps the teacher and students for gathering data systematically assessing the relevance of the data evaluation data score and making interpretive judgment based on the available data.
4. It helps for the disabled students to lead their life in better way.

Conclusion

Education is the main tool to develop the innate potentialities of an individual. It makes one to not only realize potentialities of persons but also enables one to

use them for development of one self and society. The life skills one to be developed in the process of education. There life skills enable a person to live his life effectively purposefully successfully and meaningfully so the teachers have to plan and provide optimum opportunities to the students.

This is possible only when the teachers understands the feet that the meaning of education is not more instruction of the syllabus of a text book but to prepare the individual for a happy prosperous and outstanding life in the present democratic society.

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